

Chiquinho and Buster Brown: Comic Strips and Globalization in the Early 20th Century

**Ian Gordon
Beatriz Sequeira de Carvalho**

In 1905, the journalist and caricaturist, Renato de Castro, the poet, Junior Cardoso, and the professor and journalist, Manoel Bonfim, created a new Brazilian children's magazine, *O Tico-Tico*, as part of the *O Malho* group. The first issue published October 11 featured a comic strip entitled "As Desventuras do Chiquinho." Although this strip was clearly based on the American strip Buster Brown, the first week's episode contained original art. But, by issue number 13 (the next available issue to researchers), and often for the next 15 years, *O Tico-Tico* assembled Chiquinho from the American comic strip.

In this article, we examine the first ten years or so of the Chiquinho strip. We trace its connections to the Buster Brown strip and detail how the Brazilian strip moved beyond the American original. Buster Brown appeared in other countries beyond the U.S., but nowhere else did he develop into something beyond the American character, and only in Brazil did a character drawn from Buster Brown outlast the original and indeed become a national icon. This sort of research has only become possible in the last 15 years or so with increased digitization of material, the availability of well-organized collections of comic strips at The Ohio State University's Billy Ireland Cartoon Library and Museum, and the higher quality cameras in smart phones.

Buster Brown

The creator of Buster Brown, Richard Outcault, is equally well known as the creator of the Yellow Kid. The Yellow Kid, often incorrectly described as the first comic strip, or even the first distinctive character in comics, was a figure who appeared in the pages of the *New York World*, and later, the *New York Journal-American*, starting in 1895, and gave his name to the yellow journalism of Pulitzer and Hearst. The Yellow Kid was a widely successful character, one of the crazes of fin de siècle America, whose image appeared on more products than a Marvel superhero. But, Outcault profited little from this, since he had not managed to copyright or trademark the character. The *New York Herald* published the first strip of Outcault's second major

Fig. 1. *O Tico-Tico*. Oct. 11, 1905.

Panel Translations:

1. Chiquinho has a dog named Jagunço, which is almost as naughty as the owner. One day, Chiquinho decided to play horse with Jagunço. He took a whip and...
2. He ran after the dog. The first result was not expected. The baby, who was still in her little chair, fell down off the chair and Chiquinho clashed over both of them.
3. But Chiquinho was not discouraged. He ran after Jagunço and raced quickly through the garden where his sister Zizi was walking with her doll.
4. After Chiquinho's passage, the gardener was called to help Zizi, who was head over heels.

5. Chiquinho and Jagunço got back into the house. The mother, who was packing a suitcase, had a big scare when she saw them coming ...
6. ... but could not avoid the collision. The boy and the dog went so fast that they threw the mother in the bag.
7. In the other room, the father was reading. The dog went underneath his legs and Chiquinho came right after.
8. But with the father, things was more serious and the running game ended with Chiquinho getting beat up. The beating was such that even Jagunço felt sorry.

comic character, Buster Brown, on May 4, 1902. Outcault shifted the strip to William Randolph Hearst's *New York Journal* in 1906. Having learned from his experiences with the Yellow Kid, Outcault intended right from the start to control the intellectual property in Buster Brown and sell name and image rights widely (Gordon, 1998: 43). He purchased all subsidiary rights to Buster Brown from the *Herald* in 1902 for the token sum of one dollar (*Outcault v. Lamar*, 135 A.D. 110; *Outcault v. New York Herald*, 146 F. 205; *New York Herald Co. v. Star Co.*, 146 F. 204). But, as a court case determined, he did not own the rights to "Buster Brown" as the title for a comic strip, since that had been copyrighted by the *New York Herald* as part of copyrighting the newspaper as a whole through legal deposit. After 1906, a version of Buster Brown appeared in both the *Herald* and Hearst's papers for some years. Both versions were similar enough in appearance, generally, with 12 panels, the last of which contained a resolution relating to the week's story, that only Outcault's signature on the *Journal* version and the title, Buster Brown, on the *Herald* version set them apart.

Why Outcault left the *Herald* for the *Journal* is unclear, but given his concern for his intellectual property, he may have been angered over the appearance of Buster Brown in the Paris edition of the *Herald* from Jan. 31, 1904 and, beginning in 1905, the publication of the *Herald* licensed Buster Brown books by Cupples and Leon in the U.S., and Dean and Sons in the UK. These books competed with volumes licensed by Outcault to F. A. Stokes in the U.S., and W. & R. Chambers in the UK. Once Outcault joined Hearst's *Journal*, Stokes issued books of Outcault's strip and Cupples and Leon the *Herald's* version.

Internationally, there were other versions of Buster Brown. In Italy, Buster became Mimmo Mammolo and appeared in the children's weekly paper, *Corriere dei Piccoli*, beginning with the first edition on Dec. 27, 1908. Manuela Di Franco has shown that this Italian comic strip, which used Buster Brown strips as a source, repurposed those strips to fit Italian conditions. *Corriere dei Piccoli* removed the speech balloons and replaced them with the rhyming couplets typical of much European illustrated material aimed at children. This shifted the polysemic nature of the American strip and placed Mimmo Mammolo firmly in the camp of children's literature. More broadly, "the combination of editorial choices, typographical needs, the disappearance

of speech bubbles, and the alteration of the text that makes the Italian versions an entirely different product” (Di Franco, 2023: 111). This use of Buster Brown in *Corriere dei Piccoli* was, at first, under license from the *New York Journal* with the parent company, *Corriere della Sera*, negotiating these rights (Van de Wiele, 2022: 103).

CORRIERE dei PICCOLI

ANNO I - N. 1.
SEMESTRE L. 1.50 L. M. -

SUPPLEMENTO ILLUSTRATO
del CORRIERE DELLA SERA

UFFICIO DEL GIORNALE :
VIA SOLFERINO, 1125.
MILANO.

Anno I. - N. 1.

27 Dicembre 1908.

Cent. 10 il numero.

Fig. 2. *Corriere dei Piccoli*. Dec. 27, 1908.

In Spain, Buster Brown became *Juanito y su perro* and apparently appeared from about 1905 in the sensationalist, *Los Sucesos*. These strips

Fig. 3. New York Journal-American. Jan. 27, 1907.

used speech balloons, but panels were often dropped, and the final resolution panel often was not present. *Los Sucesos* also published a series of 12 *Juanito y su perro* accordion pamphlets in 1906. These pamphlets used material from the *New York Herald*. The tenor of the gag in each strip was more or less the same, if not a literal translation, and sought to reproduce the idiomatic tone of the original. For instance, the 11th pamphlet in the series reproduced most of the June 26, 1904, episode of the Buster strip, omitting only the resolution panel. By 1909, *Los Sucesos* was using material from the Hearst-owned *New*

York Journal. The Oct. 9, 1909, issue of *Los Sucesos* reproduced much of the Sept. 19, 1909, episode in the *New York Journal*. The research of Eva Van de Wiele and Dionisio Platel shows that *Juanito y su perro* was an influential work in early 20th-Century Spain and inspired various imitators and tributes (Van de Wiele, 2019).

Fig. 4. *Juanito y su perro*. Number 11, 1906 (circa).

The Danish weekly, *Allers Famiie-Journal*, published Buster Brown strips from the Hearst newspapers under that name from at least January 1916. The strips appeared on an irregular basis with at least 23 episodes published between 1916 and mid-1921. The strips appeared in color, with 12 panels from the original, but without speech balloons. However, the text that appeared in balloons in the American original was reproduced in a faithful translation below the individual panels, reading somewhat like subtitles in a film. One other key difference is that the Danish version dropped the resolution placard and the last panel. For instance, the Jan. 20, 1916 *Allers Famiie-Journal* version of the Hearst original from Nov. 6, 1915 has Tige say: “It was lucky then that the lumbago, or whatever it’s called, went on its way right away!” rather than the long moral lesson Outcault offered in his resolution panel on the need to live in the present without dwelling on hardship, because life is short. All the *Allers Famiie-Journal* strips were from Hearst’s paper, and perhaps the proprietors of the *New York Herald* were unaware that the Danish paper was using their copyrighted comic strip name.

Antoine Sausverd has detailed the different versions of Buster Brown that appeared in France. On Jan. 31, 1904, the Paris edition of the *New York Herald* published a color comics supplement with a full-page Buster Brown strip. Like most of the Paris edition, these strips were in English. The editors of the Paris edition seem to have published the first two strips in the wrong order, since the Paris edition Jan. 31, 1904 strip only appeared on Feb. 7

in the U.S.; either that or the Bibliotheque Nationale Francaise has misfiled the digital copy available online. After Outcault left the *Herald*, the Paris edition continued to publish the *Herald* version of the strip produced by an anonymous artist until 1910. At the same time, Hachette produced comic albums of Outcault's work translated into French. These albums were derived from the F. A. Stokes volumes. In addition to these versions of Buster Brown, several ersatz versions, such as Adeline Reynaud's *Jack l'Incorrigible et son chien Puck* and *Le petit Bob et son chien Trilby*, were published early in 1900s in Paris by Capendu (Sausverdt, 2019a, 2019b).

Fig. 5. *New York Herald*. June 26, 1904.

Fig. 6. Allers Familie Journal. Jan. 23, 1916.

Fig. 7. New York Journal-American. Nov. 6, 1915.

Fig. 8. Paris Edition, *New York Herald*. Jan. 31, 1904.

Fig. 9. New York Herald. Feb. 7, 1904.

Chiquinho

Of all these versions, Chiquinho was the longest lasting, and developed to become a character quite separate from Buster Brown. Indeed, Brazilian comics scholar, Fernando Moretti, suggests that Chiquinho was so artfully adapted that Brazilians did not notice its foreign origins and, “quickly fell in love with his pranks” (Moretti, 2005: 53). In any case, it was only during the Brazilian version of the anti-comics campaigns in the 1950s, that Brazilians became aware that Chiquinho was an adaptation of Buster Brown. Just as in the UK, Australia, and France, anti-comics fervor was linked with anti-communism and concerns of local artists about the importation of foreign material (Barker, 1984; Gordon, 1986; Gordon, 2013). To show the long history of importing material, Brazilian artists revealed Chiquinho’s history (Moya, 1994: 24). It is hard to determine if Chiquinho had some sort of official imprimatur from the *Herald*, the *Journal*, and/or Outcault. There are no copyright notices attached to the Chiquinho strips, and no researcher has uncovered an archive of *O Tico-Tico* business records that might reveal any arrangements that existed. The Brazilian scholar, Roberto Elísio dos Santos, suggests that Outcault was unaware of Chiquinho, and there appears to be no extant record of legal proceedings against *O Tico-Tico* by Outcault or either the *Herald* or the *Journal* (dos Santos, 2022: 67).

O Tico-Tico was part of a shift in the production and types of magazines in Brazil. Just as elsewhere in the developed world, the process of bringing goods and services to people shifted from local to national markets created opportunities for nationally-distributed magazines relying on advertising to cover much of their costs and so, be able to build readership through low cover prices. In Brazil, for instance, publishers launched three illustrated magazines, *O Malho*, *Fon-Fon!*, and *Careta*, between 1902 and 1908. *O Malho*, launched in 1902, was aimed at a general popular audience. *Fon-Fon!* launched in 1907, appealed to a more middle-class audience. *Careta*, which began in 1908, also sought a broad audience, but was somewhat more upmarket than *O Malho*. All three relied on technological developments in printing, such as photoengraving, which allowed the production of illustrated material at a much lower cost than previous techniques. And, all looked to European and American magazines for inspiration and content (Corrêa, 2012: 71-97).

O Tico-Tico, the first children’s magazine in Brazil, was a venture of the firm that published *O Malho*. Luiz Bartolomeu de Souza e Silva and Antônio Azeredo, the two key figures of what became the Sociedade Anônima O Malho, were journalist-politicians, who believed in progress led by an intellectual class guiding the general population to a higher civilization, and both were associated with positivist thought. *O Tico-Tico*, in many ways, was a spin-off of the sort of children’s material that *O Malho*

had previously published and part of the expansion of the publishing group into a set of diverse magazines. According to Luis Bartolomeu de Souza e Silva's daughter, the magazine was named after a tico-tico, a small bird very common in southern and southeastern parts of Brazil, that landed in the family garden, where her father had been pondering a name for the new publication (Moya, 1994: 33-34). In advance of the first issue of *O Tico-Tico*, advertisements in *O Malho* made it clear that the new publication was aimed at boys and educating them to "strengthen and guide the spirit of those who will be our great men tomorrow" (Gonçalves, 2020: 260). *O Tico-Tico* did have content for girls, but that promoted a domestic maternal role for women. Displaying the international reach of the editors and publishers, *O Tico-Tico* drew inspiration from the French publications, *Le Petit Journal Illustré de la Jeunesse* and *La Semaine de Suzette* (Cardoso, 2008; de Campos and Guillier, 2024). *O Tico-Tico* was part of a larger patriarchal nationalist project that sought to place Brazil as a distinctive entity, but one situated in a modern transatlantic world. The strip, Chiquinho, was part of this endeavor, and one immediate sign of the reworking of Buster Brown for de Souza e Silva and Azeredo's goal, was the total absence in this period of Mary Jane, a regular figure in the American strip. Girls, it seemed, had a place, but not in a strip promoting values for boys. Mary Jane was so much part of the Buster Brown brand that women and girls' shoes from the Brown Shoe Company were called Mary Janes; indeed, they still are, having survived the demise of the Buster Brown shoes produced by the company.

O Tico-Tico was published until issue 2097, which carried a March-April 1962 cover date. From the 1940s though, it appeared in a reduced circumstance as a monthly, and from issue 2078, January 1959, as a bi-monthly, without any comic strips. As a children's magazine, rather than a comic strip supplement, it firmly cast its mission as educational. As Brazilian comics scholar, Waldomiro Vergueiro, has noted:

The moral and educational dimensions were at the heart of *O Tico-Tico*'s creation, constituting its very *raison d'être*. These aspects were fully understood by adults, who saw the magazine as a valuable ally in complementing their efforts to educate young Brazilians and gave it their almost unconditional support (Vergueiro, 2005).

Chiquinho appeared in the magazine until the December issue of 1958, after which time, comics disappeared from *O Tico-Tico*. Chiquinho then lasted almost 40 years longer than the Buster Brown comic strip.

In the first ten years or so, *O Tico-Tico* artists mostly traced the American strip. At first, Renato de Castro was the artist responsible for this reproduction, but, after 1907, he was joined by Luis Gomes Loureiro (Moya, 1994: 25). Loureiro took on more and more responsibility for the strip. When the source material of Buster Brown dried up, with the *Herald* discontinuing

the strip in 1911 and the *Journal* petering out in the early 1920s, Loureiro, at first, used what was available as swipe files and later developed more original strips (dos Santos, 2005: 92). Many early episodes were borrowed directly from the American Buster Brown, with wholesale tracing reproducing panels from a weekly episode almost intact, albeit, with text underneath panels rather than speech balloons of the original. Since *O Tico-Tico* had a mission of uplifting children, and, in Brazil, just as in Europe, speech balloons belonged to a coarse tradition of satire and the comic strips were perceived as children's fare, and so, in need of an educational function that was better conveyed in text under the panels. Even Buster Brown, which, in one register, was the most didactic of comic strips, was not immune to the necessity of being stripped of the crudities of speech balloons. Another way *O Tico-Tico* refigured the American originals for local audiences was by using composites of several different American strips to create fresh strips. And, all of these existed alongside originally-produced content.

Examining the early years of Chiquinho is a way of showing how Brazilian artists slowly changed the strip from a copy of Buster Brown to a strip that became closely associated with Brazilian identity. Of the 300 *O Tico-Tico* episodes of Chiquinho that I have from 1905 to 1919, 13 percent appear to be originals, created with no direct reference to a single specific episode of Buster Brown, although it is possible that I could not find the original Buster Brown episode from which it drew. Beyond these original *O Tico-Tico* strips with no clear American antecedent, there are a range of Chiquinho episodes that show that the strip, even when referencing American material, was aiming to be something different than a local Buster Brown.

Fig. 10. *O Tico-Tico*. Jan. 3, 1906.

Fig. 11. *New York Herald*. Nov. 26, 1905.

The first available issue of *O Tico-Tico* after the debut issue, dated Jan. 3, 1906, carried a Chiquinho episode assembled from the American version of November 1905. At first glance, Chiquinho seems a direct copy of the Buster Brown strip with some panels omitted. But, one panel in the Chiquinho version was repositioned later in the strip than in the Buster Brown version. Chiquinho, then, was not simply a direct reproduction with a simple translation from English to Portuguese, but a comic strip created for a Brazilian audience. The difference is subtle, to be sure, especially since,

of course, the strip, at the very least, needed to be translated for a Brazilian audience. The absence of speech balloons, the presence of text beneath the panels, and the order of panels altered, made this strip the kind of translation that refigured the comic. This Chiquinho strip is not quite in the territory that Katherine Kelp-Stebbins maps in her work on the way comics travel, but is on its way there (Kelp-Stebbins, 2022). The resolution of the scanned copy of the Jan. 3, 1906, *O Tico-Tico* is too poor to translate, but an available Chiquinho episode from three weeks later (Jan. 24, 1906), shows the way the Brazilian editors and artists produced a Brazilian comic, using Buster Brown as a basis.

Fig. 12. *New York Herald*. March 22, 1903.

In the American original from March 22, 1903, Buster buys frogs from a shop and puts them in a mail collection box. The mailman leaps in fright when he opens the box. In the *O Tico-Tico* version, in which the comic panels have no speech balloons, the illustration is explained by text, Chiquinho spends two hours walking around a farm and sneaks out of the house carrying a basket. The panel, with this action, is the same as the American strip, but for the frog shop sign being erased. In the next panel, the U.S. Mailbox has been replaced by a Brazilian version, and Chiquinho goes with his dog, Jagunço, to Avenida Central and, at the corner of Rua do Ouvidor, takes out "of the basket a bunch of strange things" before placing them in the mailbox in the next panel. Although the text in the rest of the episode is not well preserved, it is clear the joke plays out in the same fashion. While the American reader

Fig. 14. *New York Herald*. Nov. 2, 1902.

Another two-part Chiquinho published in *O Tico-Tico*, Oct. 3, and Oct. 10, 1906, reworked a *New York Herald* Nov. 2, 1902, strip. The Buster Brown strip had 10 panels and *O Tico-Tico* used the first eight, with four in each part. The American version has little text, and mostly works as a sight gag, except for the resolution panel. The *O Tico-Tico* version offers more exposition in the text under the panels and shifts the instigation of the bath to Chiquinho,

Fig. 15. *O Tico-Tico*. Sept. 12, 1906.

Panel Translations:

1. Already tired of taking so many beatings, last Sunday, Chiquinho made a very practical decision. He dressed up in a weird way, with an outfit all pulled up, and got prepared to go out on the street...
2. ... where the *O Tico-Tico* salesman and another boy, to revenge the fight from the other day, put a nail on top of a box in which Chiquinho used to sit. Chiquinho blinked an eye as he realized the wickedness ...
3. ... and sat down right on the nail. The boys were amazed by that! And besides Chiquinho, to make fun, made faces to show that everything was fine.
4. Then Chiquinho got up and left, the nail stuck in his pants. The boys were amazed and got even more so with what happened next, and you will know it in the next issue.

Fig. 16. *O Tico-Tico*. Sept. 19, 1906.

Panel Translations:

1. As we saw in the last issue, Chiquinho managed to sit on the nail and come out with it stuck in his pants, very satisfied. The boy was so angry that he kicked him ...
2. But all he got was to hurt himself. On top of that, Jagunço, seeing that outrage with his master, jumped on the boy's leg and gave him a big bite.
3. The boy stood there screaming like a madman, not understanding how Chiquinho felt nothing while he hurt himself so badly ...
4. For the secret was in a box of cigars that Chiquinho stuffed into his pants. That's why he sat so fast on the nail. And that was also why he did not bother with the spanking Mom gave him when he got home.

whereas the American version has Buster's mother instructing him to take a bath. Unlike the American version, which shows Buster's father beating him in the penultimate panel, the punishment is left un-shown and merely noted with a switch from father to mother. The gag in the resolution of never taking a bath again disappeared.

Fig. 17. *New York Herald*. Nov. 2, 1902.

Fig. 18. *O Tico-Tico*, Oct. 3, 1906.

Panel Translations:

1. The other day, Chiquinho went to the room where Mom was and said: "It's already three o'clock in the afternoon. Don't you think I can go and take a shower and change my clothes?" Mom said yes.
2. Chiquinho ran from there; but instead of going alone to the bathroom, he invited Jagunço to go with him. Jagunço hesitated a little, but in the end, decided to accompany his dear boss.
3. Chiquinho undressed and zás! ... He plunged into the water, which overflowed and splashed all over Jagunço, who was somewhat suspicious of the story.
4. The bathroom was so full that the water began to overflow with Chiquinho's movements. And our great friend, very satisfied, tried to bathe Jagunço too. Jagunço was shaking with fear. In the next issue we will see what happened.

If *O Tico-Tico* had only ever created these Brazilian strips, slightly reworking Buster Brown, then that alone would have been significant, since it shows the way humor plays across cultures. Looking at Chiquinho, we can also see the way that Outcault's polysemic strip (it appealed to the diverse audiences across the U.S. and adults, as well as children), could be reshaped as an instructional strip for children. The more raucous elements of Outcault's Buster Brown did not disappear entirely, but the language of the captions, the absence of speech balloons, and its placement in a children's magazine, gave Chiquinho a different character than Buster.

O Tico-Tico, though, did more than simply reorganize Buster Brown strips. The magazine's artists also created fresh Chiquinho strips through various acts that transposition their source material from Buster Brown. For

Fig. 19. *O Tico-Tico*. Oct. 10, 1906.

Panel Translations:

1. Finally accepting Chiquinho's invitation, who had left the faucet open, Jagunço got ready and jumped into the tub.
2. With the entrance of the nice Jagunço, the bathroom overflowed at once, flooding the whole room. And the two comrades did not even care!
3. But Mother, who ran hearing the noise, was horrified: "What is this, Chiquinho? Don't worry, you are going to take a beating!"
4. Jagunço, seeing the trouble it got in, wanted to escape, but made the situation even worse by spreading water everywhere. And this time (we're sorry to say), Chiquinho was a victim of Mom's clothes brush.

instance, a comparison of four panels from an *O Tico-Tico* June 20, 1906, strip, with their source, shows a process of bricolage. The first panel in the *O Tico-Tico* strip contains an image of Chiquinho's dog, Jagunço, that is clearly traced from the fifth panel of the *New York Herald* of Feb. 1, 1903, Buster Brown. The splash panel of the *New York Herald* of April 26, 1903, was the source for Jagunço in the second panel of the Chiquinho strip. And, in the third panel of Chiquinho, Jagunço comes from the eighth panel of the *New York Herald* of June 21, 1903, and, the fourth panel of *O Tico-Tico's* strip, makes use of the *New York Herald's* fourth panel from March 15, 1903 for both Chiquinho and Jagunço.

In these strips, *O Tico-Tico's* Chiquinho owes less and less to Buster Brown. For instance, the joke is original, and although the figures have been traced, the facial expression of Buster Brown is no longer replicated. What is significant about this strip is that it appeared less than a year after *O Tico-Tico* commenced publication. The common understanding of Chiquinho is

Fig. 20. O Tico-Tico. June 20, 1906.

Fig. 21. *New York Herald*. Feb. 1, 1903, panel 5.

Fig. 22. *New York Herald*. April 26, 1903.

Fig. 23. *New York Herald*. June 21, 1903, panel 8.

Fig. 24. *New York Herald*. March 15, 1903, panel 4.

that *O Tico-Tico* created the strip by reproducing American Buster Brown strips up until World War I, when the source material was more difficult to access (Vergueiro, 1999: 172-173; dos Santos, 2022: 67). But, clearly here, very early, Chiquinho appeared through a process of bricolage, and, in doing so, transcended its connection to Buster Brown. To be sure, instances of *O Tico-Tico* doing this were limited in these years, but my research shows there were at least 11 of this type of Chiquinho strips before 1914. Moreover, in this same period, there were 38 original episodes of Chiquinho, or at least episodes where I can't find an original. These 38 comics may, too, have been composites.

Fig. 25. *O Tico-Tico*. July 22, 1914.

A Chiquinho episode from July 22, 1914, demonstrates the way the strip evolved and mostly left behind, even the format of the American strip. This strip entitled, “Justo Castigo” [retribution], had quite a different composition and panel layout than that of Buster Brown. Chiquinho’s facial expressions differed from Buster’s, although the artist retained Buster’s haircut and red suit. Jaguço continued to be an almost and exact copy of Tige. This episode also shows the way that, beginning in 1913 Chiquinho moved from its original format of text underneath panels, to incorporating text in panels, albeit as text boxes rather than speech balloons. The gag is that Chiquinho finds one of his father’s cigarettes and after smoking, becomes so disoriented, he falls down the stairs. He, therefore, decides never to smoke again. Despite

moving away from the format of the U.S. strips, this episode, too, was created through bricolage with each panel containing figures traced from different issues of the *New York Herald*.

Fig. 26. In the first panel of *O Tico-Tico*. July 22, 1914, the model for Jagunço, is the fourth panel of the *New York Herald*. Dec. 30, 1905.

Fig. 27. In the second panel of *O Tico-Tico*. July 22, 1914, the model for Jagunço is the third panel of the *New York Herald*. Dec. 3, 1905.

Fig. 28. In the third panel of *O Tico-Tico*. July 22, 1914, the model for both Chiquinho and Jagunço is the ninth panel of the *New York Herald*. June 25, 1905.

Fig. 29. In the fourth panel of *O Tico-Tico*. July 22, 1914, the model for Chiquinho is the eighth panel of the *New York Herald*. Nov. 26, 1905.

Fig. 30. In the fourth panel of *O Tico-Tico*. July 22, 1914, the model for Jagunço is the eighth panel of the *New York Herald*. Oct. 1, 1905.

Fig. 31. In the fourth panel of *O Tico-Tico*. July 22, 1914, the model for the staircase is the seventh panel of the *New York Herald*. Jan. 1, 1906.

Fig. 32. In the fifth panel of *O Tico-Tico*. July 22, 1914, the models for the staircase landing and Chiquinho's posture are from the eighth panel of the *New York Herald*. Dec. 3, 1905.

Fig. 33. In the last panel of *O Tico-Tico*. July 22, 1914, the model for Chiquinho is the last panel of the *New York Herald*. Nov. 26, 1905.

Fig. 34. In the last panel of *O Tico-Tico*. July 22, 1914, the model for Jagunço is the last panel of the *New York Herald*. Oct. 22, 1905.

Conclusion

Chiquinho took shape through a process in which *O Tico-Tico*'s artists drew on the U.S. comic strip, *Buster Brown*, for inspiration. In a process, they moved beyond imitation of the character and developed what became a Brazilian icon of childhood. This process relied heavily on bricolage in the years up to 1920 or so. Chiquinho was one instance of the global spread of a form of comics much influenced by the American comic strip. I have shown how the American strips influenced local artists even though, as in the case in Brazil, they were aiming to create something unique.

Eike Exner has shown the U.S. influence on manga in Japan. One of Exner's examples is a *Buster Brown* episode from the *New York Journal* of Oct. 7, 1906, that he regards as the origin of a Japanese gag strip by Kitazawa Rakuten that appeared in *Tokyo Puck*, July 1, 1907 (Exner, 2021: 29-30). A third version of the gag appeared a month before Outcault's *Buster Brown* strip in the Chiquinho episode from Sept. 5, 1906.

All three strips use a sight gag and put this in the service of a broader piece of humor and commentary, and this is somewhat different in each of the three strips. What is the origin of the gag? Did Outcault have access to *O Tico-Tico* and derive his version from there? Or did the *O Tico-Tico* have pre-publication access to Outcault's strips? Perhaps, but, it is possible that

these three comics independently arrived at the gag based on another source. The widespread use and familiarity with chicken jokes had their origin in minstrelsy, and, perhaps, that is the source of all three strips. Robert Toll mentions a somewhat similar gag playing out in black minstrelsy with “incompetent masters ... running into posts while chasing chickens” (Toll, 1974: 74). The similarity between the seventh panel of the Buster strip and the third panel of Kitazawa’s strip (the latter mirrors the former) makes it certain that Exner is correct in his identification of this borrowing. But the *O Tico-Tico* strip has nothing that suggests a link, beyond the gag, to the other two strips. The three strips point to shared forms of media, mediated experience, and cultural exchange across at least three countries in the early years of the 20th Century, of which comic strips were an important part.

Fig. 35. Tokyo Puck, July 1, 1907.

304

The forms that Buster Brown took across the globe are an indication that globalization is not necessarily a one-way street. At first glance, to someone familiar with Buster Brown, Chiquinho looks instantly recognizable, but a closer examination and reading of the strip reveal a character that artists are trying to shape as Brazilian. *O Tico-Tico* was a conscious effort to use

a new style of media to inculcate a set of values in children. The magazine embodied much of the technological and social shifts that drove new forms of economic modernity around the world at the start of the 20th Century. In this regard, borrowing the Buster Brown strip seems on par with using imported rotary presses to print the magazine. But, most readers of Chiquinho were unaware of the connection and the strip became a Brazilian icon.

Fig. 36. New York American. Oct. 7, 1906.

Fig. 37. O Tico Tico. Sept. 5, 1906.

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Ian Gordon taught American history and media studies in Singapore until reaching the compulsory retirement age. He is the author of *Comic Strips and Consumer Culture* (1998), *Kid Comic Strips* (2016), *Superman: The Persistence of an American Icon* (2017), and numerous articles and several edited volumes on comics. He is a member of the international advisory board for the *Journal of American History* and a country editor for the *International Journal of Comic Art* (IJOCA).

Beatriz Sequeira de Carvalho was a graduate student at the University of Sao Paulo before wisely abandoning academia for a saner life.